

The Influence Of Providing Rewards And Reinforcement On Student Learning Outcomes In Class IV Mathematics Subjects At State Primary School 106143 Sukamaju School Year 2022/2023

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of giving rewards and reinforcement on student learning outcomes in mathematics in class IV at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju for the 2022/2023 academic year. In this study, researchers used quantitative methods. The population used was all students at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju with a sample of 31 students. Sampling using nonprobability sampling. The results of this study indicate that the results obtained from correlation test can be seen in the correlation coefficient of r (count) $0.689 \geq r$ (table) 0.355 , it can be concluded that the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, that is, there is a significant effect between reward and reinforcement on student learning outcomes at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju. It can also be seen from the results of the t-test where t (count) $> t$ (table) is t (count) of 5.113 and t (table) of 2.042 , then the hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. This shows that there is a significant positive effect between the provision of rewards and reinforcement and mathematics learning outcomes in class IV of SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju for the 2022/2023 academic year.

INTRODUCTION

Education is important for human survival, Septiana and Hayati (2019:148). Education is closely related to the transmission of knowledge, attitudes, behavior and beliefs of students along with other aspects towards self-maturation. A teacher must have the competence to support the achievement of learning goals. One of the competencies that teachers must have is the skill of providing reinforcement. Teachers in the learning process should be able to understand their students, one of which is by providing reinforcement. Reinforcement is any form of verbal or nonverbal response as feedback given to student behavior. Each student has different characteristics. These differences can be seen from students' behavior and daily life as well as when teaching and learning activities take place. Differences in student characteristics also influence student learning outcomes. Learning outcomes can be interpreted as the level of success of students in studying subject matter at school which is expressed in scores. Learning outcomes according to Susanto (Salamah, 2022:3) state that learning outcomes are changes that occur in students, both affective and psychomotor as a result of learning activities.

In relation to learning outcomes, mathematics learning is still a topic among stakeholders and society. This is because in studying mathematics people have to think so that they are able to understand these concepts correctly. According to Priatna (Salamah, 2022:3) explains that if a child is studying mathematics then the child is essentially honing his intelligence directly. This is because a person's level of intelligence is closely related to the ability to think, reason and imagine. Mathematics is a subject that requires a logical and systematic level of thinking, so that many students are not used to following the learning process optimally, especially high class students who should be mature and able to be encouraged to think logically and be able to obtain good results.

Based on the results of a pre-survey conducted by researchers at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju Class IV. Teachers have already implemented giving rewards and reinforcement in learning to students. However, implementation has not been optimal. Due to the impact of the COVID-19 virus, students play and use social media too much so they no longer pay attention to the rewards and reinforcement given by their teachers. Some students also do not submit their assignments and some students do not follow the learning flow at school. So there is a bad influence on student learning outcomes.

Table 1 Mathematics Scores Semester I Class IV SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju

No	KKM	MARK	LOTS OF STUDENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	70	≥ 70	10	32%
2		< 70	21	68%
AMOUNT			31	100%

Source: List of Class IV Grades at State Elementary School 106143 Sukamaju

Based on table 1.1, the test results for class IV students were 31 students in mathematics. There were 10 students who obtained test scores above the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) out of 31 students (32%), with a score of ≥ 70 . Meanwhile, 21 students out of 31 students (68%) received test scores above the Maximum Completeness Criteria (KKM), with scores < 70 . Meanwhile, the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) for mathematics lessons at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju is 70. The number of students whose scores are below the KKM is greater than the number of students whose scores are above the KKM.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding Rewards

According to Sohimin (2018:157) rewards are rewards, prizes, awards, or rewards. Rewards as an educational tool are given when a child does something good, has successfully reached a certain stage of development, or achieved a target. In the concept of education, rewards are a tool to increase students' motivation. This model can associate a person's actions and behavior with feelings of happiness, pleasure, and will usually make them do a good deed repeatedly. Apart from motivation, rewards also aim to encourage someone to become more active in their efforts to improve or improve the achievements they have achieved.

Basics and Principles of Giving Rewards

Some basics and principles of giving rewards according to experts are below. According to Kompri (2018:292), several basics for giving rewards to students are:

- a) Rewards from educators should decrease as students progress further. With the aim that students no longer expect appreciation from others but from themselves in their lives.
- b) Awards are given wisely, meaning that a child may commit unsportsmanlike actions in order to get an award, in other words, if the award given creates an arrogant attitude then giving the award must be stopped.
- c) Awards are given fairly, without discriminating between students, not only for being diligent, serious and persistent in trying.
- d) Awards are given according to the nature and character of the students. Give it to children who need it more than other children, for example giving it to younger children rather than older children.

Forms of Giving Rewards

According to Najamudin (Khofifa, 2022:5) in the context of education, there are four forms of reward, namely:

- a) Praise words such as: good, good, very good and so on. Praise as a form of reward is the easiest action to implement. Likewise, praise can take the form of showing the thumb, patting the shoulder accompanied by words of praise, and applause.
- b) Respect for successful children. This form of respect takes the form of crowning the child in front of his friends as an exemplary student or an achiever at the end of the school year. Apart from that, respect can also give power to children who are more and achiever to do something in accordance with the field that is liked by the child's achievement.
- c) Gifts or gifts in the form of goods. This reward is also called material reward. Of course, it should be adjusted to the child's needs at school to make it easier for him to improve his performance and be seen by other children.
- d) Sign of appreciation. The form of reward is not in the form of goods but in a statement or certificate as a symbol of appreciation given for the achievements achieved by students.

Purpose of Giving Rewards

Providing rewards aims to enable students to increase their learning activities so that they can improve their learning outcomes. Rewards given by the teacher can be in the form of praise, snacks, star symbols, applause and so on. According to Shoimin (2018:157) apart from motivation, rewards also aim to make someone become more active in their efforts to improve or increase the achievements they have achieved.

Meanwhile, according to Febianti (2018:99) rewards or awards function as reinforcement given by teachers to students, aimed at increasing concentration, activeness and motivation, as well as fostering students' attitudes in a positive direction in teaching and learning activities, can be given in various ways. differ based on the situations and conditions that occur when learning activities take place. The rewards given must be on target so that they provide deep meaning for students. The rewards given must also create a pleasant and conducive atmosphere for.

Steps for Giving Rewards

In giving rewards there are also steps that will be carried out in the learning process. According to Sari (2017:6) The steps of the reward method can be seen as follows:

1. In the middle of explaining the material being taught, the teacher inserts or gives practice questions according to the lesson material given/taught.
2. Students who are active in answering correctly receive rewards, for example with words that arouse students' interest in learning. For example, good, good, smart.
3. Students who make noise in class or are lazy about studying are given the opportunity to answer questions.

4. If you answer correctly you will be given a reward, but if you answer incorrectly and are proven to have caused a commotion, you will receive a reward according to the level of error.

Understanding Providing Reinforcement

Reinforcement is all forms of response, verbal/non-verbal in nature, part of modifying teacher behavior towards student behavior, by providing information or feedback as a goal for the recipient (student) for their actions, as encouragement or correction. According to Febianti (2018:97) reinforcement is a response to behavior that can increase the possibility of the behavior recurring. A teacher must master teaching skills. One of the skills that teachers must master is the skill of providing reinforcement, Septiana and Hayati (2019:148).

Sanjaya (in Septiana and Hayati, 2019: 148) says "reinforcement is any form of response which is part of modifying teacher behavior towards student behavior, which aims to provide information or feedback for students for actions or responses given as encouragement or correction

Types of Reinforcement Providing

Rusman (2014:84), as a good teacher must always provide reinforcement, both in verbal and non-verbal form.

- a) Verbal reinforcement is reinforcement expressed in the form of direct words. Like a hundred for you, excellent, very good, good job, just right
- b) Non-verbal reinforcement is this reinforcement which is usually carried out by movement, gesture, touch, caress, approach and so on, which is part of the modification of teacher behavior towards student behavior which aims to provide information or feedback (feedback) for students for good deeds as a encouraging action so that the action continues to be repeated.

Purpose of Providing Reinforcement

Providing reinforcement is not only when learning has a specific goal. According to Djamah (Kurniawan, 2018:76) reinforcement has the following objectives:

- a) Increases student attention and helps students learn when reinforcement is used selectively.
- b) Providing motivation to students
- c) Used to control or change disruptive student behavior and improve productive learning methods.
- d) Develop students' confidence to self-manage learning experiences.
- e) Directs towards the development of divergent thinking and taking free initiative.
- f) Makes it easier for students to learn
- g) Control and modify student behavior and encourage positive behavior.
- h) Growing students' self-confidence.

- i) Maintain a conducive classroom climate.

Understanding Learning

According to Jihad and Haris (2013: 1) learning is a process activity and is a very fundamental element in the implementation of types and levels of education, this means that the success of achieving educational goals is very dependent on the success of students' learning processes in schools and the surrounding environment.

Meanwhile, Gadge (in Hariyanto Agus, 2019:2) learning is a process where an organization changes its behavior as a result of experience. Experience is an event that is received by the five senses as a concrete form of communication with other people or the environment. The experience gained is learning that causes physical and non-physical changes in a person. The activities carried out are the results of what is heard, felt and seen as an experience.

Learning Principles

The learning principles in question are concepts or understanding of learning that can be implemented in different situations and conditions by each student individually. According to Fathurrohman and Sulystiorini (2013:17) learning principles are concepts that must be applied in the teaching and learning process. A teacher will be able to carry out his duties well if he can apply teaching methods that are in accordance with learning principles. Several learning principles, namely:

- a) Whatever the student learns, he is the one who must learn, not anyone else. For this reason, students must act actively.
- b) Each student learns according to his or her level of ability.
- c) Students will be able to learn well if they receive direct reinforcement for every step taken during the learning process.
- d) Perfect mastery and every step taken by students will make the learning process more meaningful.
- e) Students' learning motivation increases if they are given full responsibility and trust for their learning

Understanding Learning Outcomes

Learning outcomes are the abilities that children gain after going through learning activities, Abdurrahman (Jihad & Haris, 2013:14). Learning itself is a process of someone trying to obtain a relatively permanent form of behavior change. According to Susanto (2014: 5) learning outcomes can be interpreted as the level of success of students in studying learning material at school which is expressed in scores from test results regarding a number of certain subject materials. In the sense that learning outcomes can be seen from the test results obtained by students on certain subject matter.

Factors that Influence Learning Outcomes

Development itself requires something both from oneself and influences from the environment. According to Susanto, (2013:12) based on theory, student

learning outcomes are influenced by two things, the students themselves and their environment. First, students in the sense of thinking or intellectual behavior, motivation, interest and readiness of students, both physically and spiritually. Second, the environment, namely facilities and infrastructure, teacher competence, teacher creativity, learning resources, methods and support from the environment, family and environment.

Relevant Research Results

Research conducted by Rudolf Rejekki Sitohang (2023) was entitled "The Effect of Giving Rewards and Reinforcement on Student Learning Outcomes in Class V Mathematics Subjects". This research aims to determine the effect of providing rewards and reinforcement on student learning outcomes in class V mathematics subjects at SDN 064981 Medan Helvetia. In this research, researchers used quantitative methods. The population used is all elementary school students. 064981 Medan Helvetia with a sample of 61 students. Sampling was taken using nonprobability sampling. Results of this research shows that the results obtained from correlation testing can be seen in the correlation coefficient of $0.279 \geq 0.254$, so it can be concluded that the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, namely that there is a significant influence between the provision of rewards and reinforcement on the learning outcomes of elementary school students. 064981 Helvetia Field. It can also be seen from the results of the t-test where $>$ namely 2.234 and 2.000, then the hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. This shows that there is a significant positive influence between the provision of rewards and reinforcement and mathematics learning outcomes in class V SDN. 064981 Helvetia Field.

Framework of Thinking

Providing rewards and reinforcement in learning to students is very necessary and very important. However, in higher level schools it can be adjusted according to age and needs. By providing rewards and reinforcement, it is hoped that learning outcomes can improve, the learning process is better, and learning motivation increases. The teacher's competence in providing rewards and reinforcement must also be considered in its implementation so that the rewards and reinforcement given have meaning and benefits for students. The following is a chart of how teachers can implement rewards and reinforcement.

Figure 2.1 Framework for Thinking

METHODOLOGY

The type of approach used in this research is a quantitative approach. In this research, researchers used a quantitative survey type method. In this research, judging from the data used, this research is quantitative research. In this research there are 2 variables, namely the independent variable and the dependent variable. The first variable is the independent variable, namely "reward and reinforcement" which is given the letter notation (X) and the second is the dependent variable, namely "learning outcomes" which is given the letter notation (Y). The design used in this research is as follows.

Figure 3.1 Research Design

The population in this study were students at SD Negeri 064981 Medan Helvetia who were used as subjects in the research, so the sample in this study was class V students at SDN 064981 Medan Helvetia, totaling 61 students. The quantitative data in this research is in the form of students' mathematics learning outcomes. This research uses data sources, namely primary data sources that can be directly given to research subjects or data collectors. In research, the data collection techniques carried out by researchers are questionnaires and documentation. Before testing the hypothesis, data normality testing will first be carried out. To determine whether the distribution of data is normal or not, researchers used Kolmogorov-Smirnov analysis with the help of the SPSS Version 22.0 program.

The calculation results show that the data is normally distributed if the value of Asymp. Sign is greater than > 0.05 . On the other hand, the value of Asymp. The sign is smaller than < 0.05 , then the data can be said to be not normally distributed. Asymp value. This sign tests the significance of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test calculation results. To determine whether there is an influence between the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y), the Pearson Product Moment correlation formula is used with the help of SPSS Version 22.0. Researchers use the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. In this research, the t test was used to determine the extent to which the variable (X) providing rewards and reinforcement by teachers has an influence on the variable (Y) student learning outcomes. To determine the effect of each variable, researchers used the t test.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The purpose of carrying out descriptive analysis is to determine the condition of a variable so that the data has meaning and significance. Descriptive analysis is carried out by processing the data obtained, then arranging it in an orderly manner, so that it is easier to understand. Research data obtained by researchers from class IV students at SDN 106143 Sukamaju,

research data consists of one independent variable, namely, giving rewards and reinforcement (X) and the dependent variable, namely, learning outcomes (Y). Data on the independent variable giving rewards and reinforcement (X) was obtained from a questionnaire, with a Likert scale answer model with 4 (four) answer options distributed to 31 students. The data obtained from the questionnaire was then tabulated to make data processing easier.

Meanwhile, the learning outcome variable data (Y) uses the average grade of the odd semester report cards for the 2022/2023 academic year. The purpose of carrying out descriptive analysis is to determine the condition of a variable so that the data has meaning and significance. Descriptive analysis is carried out by processing the data obtained, then arranging it in an orderly manner, so that it is easier to understand. Research data obtained by researchers from class IV students at SDN 106143 Sukamaju, research data consists of one independent variable, namely, giving rewards and reinforcement (X) and the dependent variable, namely, learning outcomes (Y). Data on the independent variable giving rewards and reinforcement (X) was obtained from a questionnaire, with a Likert scale answer model with 4 (four) answer options distributed to 31 students. Meanwhile, the learning outcome variable data (Y) uses the average grade of the odd semester report cards for the 2022/2023 academic year. Frequency distribution of data for the variable providing reward and reinforcement can be seen below:

Table 2 Frequency Distribution of Reward and Reinforcement
 Questionnaire Results

Frequency Distribution						
X	F	Xi	FXi	$X=Xi-x$	X ²	F.X ²
64-69	1	66.5	66.5	- 11.53225806	132.9929761	132.9929761
70-75	16	72.5	1160	- 5.532258065	30.60587929	489.6940687
76-81	5	78.5	392.5	0.467741935	0.218782518	1.093912591
82-87	3	84.5	253.5	6,467741935	41.83168574	125.4950572
88-93	4	90.5	362	12.46774194	155.444589	621.7783559
94-99	2	96.5	193	18.46774194	341.0574922	682.1149844
Total	31		2427.5			2053.169355

Based on the diagram of providing rewards and reinforcement above, it can be concluded that the provision of rewards and reinforcement at SDN 106143 Sukamaju is in the low category. The frequency distribution of student mathematics learning outcome variable data can be seen below:

Table 3
Frequency Distribution of Student Mathematics Learning Outcomes

Frequency Distribution						
X	F	Xi	FXi	$X=Xi-x$	X ²	F.X ²
60-64	10	62	620	-7.193548387	51.7471384	517,471
65-69	11	67	737	-2.193548387	4.811654527	52.9282
70-74	3	72	216	-66,19354839	4381.585848	13144.8
75-79	0	77	0	7.806451613	60.94068678	0
80-84	5	82	410	12.80645161	164.0052029	820,026
85-89	2	87	174	17.80645161	317.069719	634,139
Total	31		2157			15169.3

Based on the diagram of student learning outcomes above, it can be concluded that the mathematics learning outcomes of students at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju are in the low category at 35%. The Normality Test is carried out to determine whether the data taken comes from a normally distributed population or not. The Normality Test is carried out on the two variables to be

studied, namely the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y). Researchers conducted a statistical normality test with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistics test at an alpha of 5%. If the significant value from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is greater (>) than 0.05 then the data is normally distributed, whereas if it is smaller (<) than 0.05 then the data is not normally distributed.

Table 4 Instrument Normality Test
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residuals
N		31
Normal	Mean	.0000000
Parameters, b	Std. Deviation	6.16623263
Most Extreme	Absolute	.125
Differences	Positive	,097
	Negative	-.125
Statistical Tests		.125
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200c,d

Based on the normality test above using SPSS with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (KS), a significant value of 0.200 was obtained which was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$ ($0.200 \geq 0.05$) then it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. This research uses correlation analysis using the r_{xy} formula to prove that there is a significant influence between the independent variables (X) reward and reinforcement on the dependent variable (Y) student learning outcomes.

Table 5 Correlation Test Results of Giving Rewards and Reinforcement to Learning Outcomes
Correlations

		Reward and Reinforcement	MARK
Reward and Reinforcement	Pearson Correlation	1	,689**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000
	N	31	31
MARK	Pearson Correlation	,689**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	
	N	31	31

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.689 with a significance of 0.000. Meanwhile r_{tabel} with $N=31$ of 0.355. From the results of these calculations it can be seen that $r_{hitung} \geq r_{tabel}$ ($0.689 \geq 0.355$), then it

can be concluded that the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, namely that there is a significant positive influence between giving rewards and reinforcement (X) and student learning outcomes (Y) at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju class IV.

Table 6 Hypothesis Testing Coefficientsa

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	10,623	11,511		,923	,364
Reward and Reinforcement	,751	,147	,689	5.113	,000

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the value t_{hitung} amounting to 5,113 while for t_{tabel} 2,750, then $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$ ($5.113 > 2.042$), so it can be concluded that H_a is accepted, namely that there is a significant influence between providing rewards and reinforcement on student learning outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This research was conducted at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju. Researchers used questionnaires as a tool to collect data with a total research sample of 31 students. Sampling in this study used non-probability sampling. The aim of the researchers in conducting this research was to determine the effect of providing rewards and reinforcement on student learning outcomes at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju.

1. Providing Rewards and Reinforcement

It is very necessary for teachers to provide rewards and reinforcement in the classroom. Rewards as an educational tool are given when a child does something good, or has succeeded in reaching a certain stage of development or achieving a target. Reinforcement can be interpreted as a response to a behavior that can increase the likelihood of the behavior repeating itself. From the results of the analysis of the frequency of giving rewards and reinforcement that has been carried out, it is in the very high category at 6%. The frequency of providing rewards and reinforcement in the high category is 13%. The frequency of providing rewards and reinforcement in the sufficient category is 10%. The frequency of providing rewards and reinforcement in the less than category is 16%. The frequency of providing rewards and reinforcement in the low category is 52%. The frequency of providing rewards and reinforcement in the very low category is 3%. Based on the results of the analysis of the frequency of giving rewards and reinforcement that researchers have carried out, the researchers found that the results of the questionnaire data on giving rewards and reinforcement at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju had an average score of 78.03 in the low category.

2. Learning Outcomes

Results Learning includes three domains, namely: cognitive domain, affective domain and psychomotor domain. From the results of research conducted by researchers, the learning outcomes in the very high category are 6%. The frequency of the high category is 16%. The category frequency is sufficient at 0%. The frequency of the category is less than 10%. The low category frequency is 35%. The frequency of the category is very low at 32%. In this way, researchers obtained student learning outcomes at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju through documentation studies which had an average score of 69.19 in the low category.

3. The Effect of Providing Rewards and Reinforcement on Learning Outcomes

Providing rewards and reinforcement has an influence on student learning outcomes. A student who often gets rewards and reinforcement from teachers at school will be different from a student who rarely gets rewards and reinforcement. Students who often receive rewards and reinforcement will be more active in learning, enthusiastic about doing their assignments, and will get good learning results. However, in this case the teacher should not be careless in providing rewards and reinforcement, he must pay attention to the basis and principles of giving as well as the form in which it will be given.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing as well as discussion of research carried out on class IV students at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju for the 2022/2023 academic year, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The provision of rewards and reinforcement at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju is in the low category, an average of 78.03. The forms of reward and reinforcement are as follows: rewards in the form of praise, respect, gifts and tokens of appreciation and reinforcement in verbal and nonverbal forms.
2. Mathematics learning results for fourth grade students at SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju for 31 students with an average of 69.19 in the low category.

There is a significant influence between providing rewards and reinforcement on student learning outcomes in class IV of SD Negeri 106143 Sukamaju for the 2022/2023 academic year. This is proven by $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$ namely, $5.113 > 2.042$ with a significance of 0.01 which means H_a is accepted, namely that giving rewards and reinforcement has an influence on learning outcomes

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Based on the conclusions of research results that have been carried out using scientific procedures, however, the research results have limitations, namely:

1. This research was carried out in a relatively short time so the results were not optimal.
2. When the researchers distributed the questionnaire, there were still respondents who did not understand how to fill in the answers to the questionnaire/statements, so that when the respondents filled in the answers to the questionnaire they were given, they did not show the actual situation or the answers did not correspond to what actually happened.

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